

THE REFLECTION OF TALENT, SPIRIT, AND REBELLION IN FEMALE LITERATURE

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Abstract: In modern literary studies, the need for special approaches to the question of talent in the analysis of artistic works and evaluation of creativity is increasingly being proven. The article discusses views on the issue of female image, spirit, rebellion and talent in literature.

Keywords: “talent”, “soul”, “rebellion”, “person», “poet”, “poem”, “prose”, “equality”, “inequality”, “spirit”, “female author”, “feminist literature”, “justice” and “injustice”.

The analysis and research of the spiritual and cultural heritage, critical study of current literary process phenomena, mastering, and aesthetic evaluation form the basis of literary science. In world literary studies, the method of revealing reality by relying on symbols, symbols and signs, mainly the study and analysis of feminist literature in literature, began to be studied. In this regard, psychological works have begun to be published, which focus on the evolutions occurring in the heart, soul, and spirit of modern writers. However, because literature was considered a man's business, women endured for centuries and created under male pseudonyms, but in the last century, women began to show strong protest against degrading insults. Just as time series affects human thinking, great changes take place in literature, which is its product. During the Shura era, it was strong to cover the outer world, «beautiful life» and interesting moments of a person in stories, but after the 80s of this period, it became a tradition to look at literature with a different eye, to penetrate into the human psyche, and to cover the evolutions taking place in the thinking. There have also been significant updates to the image object and expression methods. During this period, the desire to show the artistic expression of the revisions in the psyche of female authors, both in verse and in prose, increased. The protest of the creators created a unique voice and their work became important in literature. In recent years, many new terms have been reflected in scientific research in this direction, among which the most famous are: «talent», «spirit», «rebellion», «personality», «poet, «gender», androgyny”, “women's ethics», «feminist literature», «patriarchy», etc. are among them. In literature, the issue of inequality in views of female and male literature is connected and researched not only with literary work, but also with various aspects of social and cultural

life. Because creativity and talent belong to the soul, and a poem or a work is a product of mental processes, and the body (body) has absolutely nothing to do with it. The study of feminist literature, the writing style of poets and writers who began to write with a new intensity, and the issue of deep understanding of the author's unique spiritual world is considered one of the most important tasks in literary studies. It should be said that women in many ways did not have the same position in society as men, and usually most of them had to choose and create masculine names as pseudonyms in order to avoid unfair criticism, including: Charlotte Bronte (Carrer Bell), Emily Bronte (Ellis Bell) , Anne Bronte (Acton Bell), Louise May Olcott (A.M. Bernard), Mary Evans (George Eliot), Karen Blixen (Pierre Andrezel), Joan Rowling (J.K. Rowling), Zinaida Gippius (Nikita Vecher) , Amandina Aurora Lucille Dupin (George Sand), Svetlana Martinchik (Max Fry), so this line can be continued for a long time. Most of the female poets, writers, translators and publicists spoke out against discrimination and inequality in the society. Gradually, public rebellions began to appear in the works of the artists whose names were mentioned above.

In the emergence of this drastic change in the mentality of women, in fact, the service of male creators is great [1].

The reason is that they were the first to raise the issue of what is the role of a woman in society, that she is a person, and that she should also be considered a person. Including L.N. Tolstoy «Anna Karenina», Gustave Flaubert «Madame Bovary», Stendhal «Red and Black», Ferdinand Duchene «Tamilla», A.S. Pushkin with strong and happy characters in works such as «Eugene Onegin», «Boris Godunov», Nikolai Cherneshevsky «What should be done?», Alexander Dumas «Queen Margot», from Uzbek literature Abdulla Kadiri's novels «Gone Days», «Scorpion from the Altar», Cholpon's «Night and Day», Gafur Ghulam's short story «Netay», in short, several thousands of similar works, the success of the female heroes in the society, sometimes the tragic fate, the consequences of their struggle and submissiveness motivated women to fight for their place. Thus, «Who is a woman?» raised the issue. Thus, «Who is man?» «Who is the person?» In order to find answers to these questions, the importance of gender roles in society began to be studied.

We know that the pains of the society have always been reflected in literature and thus immortal works have been created. It's no secret that women who are humiliated in society have become the immortal heroes of great works. The attitude towards the gender role of a woman is visible not only in society, but also in the literary scene. Despite the fact that both of them perform the same

role in society, their activities are distinguished from those of men. For example, in English literature, men are still called “writers” and women are called “female writers”, Russian literature is also free of such distinctions. It cannot be said. The fact that words such as poet (male poet), poetess (female poet), pisatel (male writer) and pisatelnitsa (female writer) are still widely used, as if there should be a biological difference in literature, clearly proves our point. It should be said that Uzbek literature is not compatible with such views. Men are called poets and writers, women are called poets and writers. The most interesting thing is that in other genres, for example, journalism, dramaturgy, essay writing, literary criticism, such distinctions are not visible for some reason.

In the West, women's creativity was not taken seriously for many years, while in the East, women artists were somewhat highlighted when the Kokan literary environment was created. In the West, the idea that men create “works” and women write emotional experiences aimed at women has been put forward, and the examples of creativity written by female authors have been evaluated as simple, weepy views, or men write about important issues related to humanity, while women only express their feelings that interest them.”, was evaluated as [2]. However, despite how many names are recognized, literary studies by literary scholars of works written by men and women have raised such questions, and it is also known that there are far fewer women authors than men. Research shows that the most prominent literary theories are based on male texts, and women's works are not studied and ignored because they are considered not to meet the criteria of these theories. This is related to the fact that the names of women authors and the study of the history of their work have also been forgotten. But due to the existence of such views, sometimes hidden and sometimes open rebellions began to appear in the work of women who created all times, not only in society, but also in literature [3].

But no matter what they do, the role of creators is incomparable, just as female characters play an extremely important role in literature. Considering this, it has been observed that modern women writers often write in the first person because they take the entire position of the subject and feel the experiences of the protagonist very deeply[4]. However, scientific discussions are still going on in this regard by literary experts.

The concept of gender in literary studies appeared at the end of the 20th century, that is, after it began to be widely used in linguistics. Research in this direction was also conducted mainly on the study of the characteristics of male dominance in literature and society. At the end of the 20th century, the articles

of the first foreign authors began to be published (M. Ryutkenen, G. Brandt, E. Shore, M. Abasheva, E. Trofimov), artistic texts were focused on the issues of studying women's literature and the image of women in literature under gender studies in literary studies. [5].

«The body is like Mary. Each of us has Jesus within us. If we have pain like Mary, our Jesus will be born. If there is no pain, it will go back the way it came», that is, our Jesus will not be born. Therefore, if we connect the above narration of Maulana Rumi with the birth of the poem, literary experts connect such a phenomenon with dualism in literary studies, that is, the existence of aspects characteristic of masculinity and femininity in one person. It is known that thoughts about dualism actually arose in philosophy first, and it was first introduced to science as a term by the German philosopher H. Wolff. According to the scientist, this meant the recognition of two different substances: material and spiritual. However, the French philosopher René Descartes expanded the idea of H. Wolff and continued his scientific research in this regard. Based on his research, the first substance is capable of perception - the Spirit, it understands everything, and the second, that is, the material substance, which acts as a space for this spirit - the Body (body), thus, the scientist proves that psychological and physiological processes in a person are different from each other. Then, on the basis of gender studies, we can conclude that the role of female authors in literature is completely different from their biological origin.

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